

Research Symposium: A Multifaceted Exploration of Elections in the MENA Region

Introduction

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The study of electoral processes under the autocratic or semi-autocratic regimes in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region is fraught with challenges. These challenges emanate not only from the operational constraints of conducting research within such political landscapes but also from a deep-seated skepticism regarding the significance of such studies and the actual meaning of electoral processes in such contexts. Despite this, the MENA region, known for a complex political terrain marked by autocratic governance that was not permeable to the different waves of democratization that reached the rest of the world, and even remained resilient after the Arab Revolts of 2011, has seen a notable uptick in scholarly interest. This symposium tries to show a glimpse of the intricate dynamics of electoral politics within these regimes, drawing upon a rich tapestry of case studies that shed light on the multifaceted roles elections play in shaping the political narrative of the region.

The electoral processes in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region are often considered as tools used by authoritarian regimes to maintain their power. This criti-

cism stems from the perception that MENA elections fall far short of democratic ideals. But, indicators like those from the Electoral Integrity Project (EIP), challenge the notion of a vast gap in perceived electoral integrity between MENA and Western democracies. Notably, the EIP's 2023 report found a higher perception of electoral integrity in Qatar (rated 65) compared to the United States (rated 64), despite Qatar's 'Closed Autocracy' classification versus the US's 'Liberal Democracy' (Garnett et. al., 2023, 6) This highlights a disconnect: how elections are perceived in non-democratic regimes may differ from how they are categorized based on established democratic principles. Therefore, assessing electoral integrity necessitates a broader perspective that extends beyond the formal architecture of the system and its influence on the polity of MENA states. It involves delving into the significance and interest these elections truly evoke among voters, as evidenced by empirical data. This comprehensive approach highlights the importance of understanding the nuanced motivations and engagements of the electorate, thereby providing a more holistic view of electoral dynamics and their implications for democratic progress in the region. MENA elections, far

from mere formalities, can be pivotal events impacting domestic and international politics despite the arguably lack of interest that they can generate among the general public. The objective of this symposium is then to explore the inherent value these elections hold for governments, candidates, and voters, despite not being fully democratic. It seeks to unravel the underlying meanings and implications of electoral participation in such contexts.

The authors' contributions are the product of a two-round workshop on electoral politics held during 2023 at the Gulf Studies Center, Qatar University, the workshop was jointly organized by the SEPAD Project at Lancaster University and the Observatory on Politics and Elections of the Arab and Muslim World, Spain. The event showcased over 20 papers examining electoral processes across the region, from Morocco to Pakistan, signifying the depth and breadth of contemporary academic exploration into this area. By highlighting these efforts, this symposium acknowledges the critical role of scholarly research in enhancing our understanding of electoral politics in the MENA region. Thanks are due to Dr. Daniel L. Tavana who has solicited the contributions, edited the pieces, and worked closely with the authors to put together this symposium.

In 'Ethno-Religious Minorities and Electoral Politics in Iran', Mansour Anbarmoo and Edward Wastnidge address the participation of ethnic and religious minorities in Iran's elections, focusing on Sunni-dominated provinces of Sistan and Baluchistan, Kurdistan, and West Azerbaijan. The contribution reveals how shifts in government policies have influenced minority participation rates, painting a picture of evolving political engagement within the Islamic Republic. Their analysis

shows that voter turnout in these provinces often differs from the national average, with early years showing lag but later aligning more closely or exceeding national participation rates. They highlight the influence of reformist candidates on increasing minority participation and the role of local Sunni leaders in mobilizing voter turnout. The piece also traces the Iranian government's policies towards minorities over different administrations, from focusing on security and economic reform to more inclusive civil society efforts under Khatami and recent shifts towards securitization under Raisi. They eloquently show how while Iran's minorities have historically faced challenges in political participation, recent electoral trends present a complex picture of engagement, influenced by local leadership and national political dynamics.

Chantal Sarkis' 'The Evolution of Electoral Representation and Internal Conflicts in Lebanon' examines Lebanon's confessional representation system and its impact on the country's internal conflicts and electoral system from the 19th century to the present. She details the historical development of the system, starting with the division of Mount Lebanon into two regions in 1841, leading to the establishment of the *moutassarifya* system and eventually the Ta'if Accords in 1989 that ended the civil war with modified power-sharing arrangements. Sarkis argues for an electoral system that not only ensures effective representation but also promotes inter-community cooperation. Her analysis of Lebanon's electoral history demonstrates the challenges and evolution towards achieving a balance between accurate group representation and fostering spaces for inter-group cooperation, and how electoral and institutional engineering can contribute to overcome the differences among different groups.

Zeidon Alkinani's piece 'Iraq's Electoral Political Dynamics: Traditional Structures vis-à-vis Reformist Tendencies' explores the evolving landscape of Iraq's parliamentary electoral system since its establishment in 2005, highlighting the enduring ethnic-sectarian power-sharing system known as the *muhasasa* system, and the emergence of reformist forces challenging traditional Islamist political parties. It delves into the consequences of the 2019 Tishreen protest movement, which prompted significant political transformations, including governmental resignations, electoral law amendments, and the rise of independent candidates, despite the subsequent reassertion of traditional parties' dominance. Furthermore, the analysis examines the latest 2023 provincial elections, emphasizing the Coordination Framework's manipulation of electoral outcomes to maintain power and thwart potential opposition, reflecting broader issues of electoral integrity and democratic reform in Iraq.

Simon Mabon's piece, 'Why do anti-sectarian protesters vote for sectarian parties?', complements Alkinani and Sarkis pieces, as it investigates the paradox where anti-sectarian protesters in Iraq and Lebanon, despite their vocal opposition to sectarian politics, ended up voting for sectarian parties in subsequent elections. Drawing on a comprehensive survey conducted in 2021 across both countries, the study highlights the profound frustration with socio-economic conditions and government performance, alongside a deep-seated resentment towards sectarian elites. Despite widespread dissatisfaction, the results underscored a pragmatic choice by many voters who, faced with existential crises, viewed sectarian parties as capable of providing necessary support for survival. Mabon suggests that this outcome reflects the complex interplay between ideal visions of politics free

from sectarianism and the harsh material realities of daily life, underpinned by the sectarian parties' ability to offer material support in times of need. His analysis sheds light on the enduring influence of sectarian identities in political life and the challenging process of desectarianization in both states.

Courtney Freer's research, 'Effects of Single Non-transferrable Vote (SNTV) Systems on Tribal Representation: Preliminary Findings from Jordan and Kuwait' explores the impact of the SNTV system on tribal representation in both monarchies, highlighting its largely ineffective role in diminishing tribal votes in Kuwait and its partial success in Jordan, specifically against tribes antagonistic to the regime. The study delves into the SNTV's strategic disadvantages for organized political groups, like tribes, and its role as a tool for monarchies to control electoral outcomes without significantly altering the tribal composition within parliaments. Despite expectations, the SNTV system reinforced tribal identities at the polls in Jordan and did not significantly alter the tribal representation in Kuwait, where tribes remain a potent political force, demonstrating the complex interplay between electoral systems and tribal politics in hybrid regimes.

Finally, Rafael Bustos' piece, 'When and how elections can be drivers for conflict transformation: transitional justice and peacebuilding in WANA societies,' delves into a very current topic, how elections can facilitate conflict transformation and support peacebuilding in West Asia and North Africa (WANA), focusing on Algeria, Tunisia, Sudan, and Jordan. Bustos argues that elections can either exacerbate or mitigate conflicts, contributing to social peace through power sharing or fueling further divisions. Through a dual analytical framework that assesses the contexts of re-

gime change, armed conflict, authoritarian rule, and the role of inclusive processes, Bustos identifies distinct dynamics of elite and social inclusion or exclusion in the studied countries. The findings reveal varying degrees of integration and exclusion across cases, with electoral and constitutional designs playing crucial roles in shaping these dynamics and their impact on transitional justice and conflict transformation efforts.

The analysis presented in these six contributions underscore the critical role electoral system designs play across a range of contexts characterized by diverse ethno-linguistic, tribal, and religious divisions. These factors are equally as impactful as the ideological-political cleavages found in many democratic regimes. Together, the pieces shine a light on numerous obstacles to inclusive and equitable political participation, including the impacts of sectarian politics, ethnic-sectarian power-sharing arrangements, and electoral outcome manipulations. Such challenges are portrayed as pivotal elements influencing electoral integrity and the pursuit of democratic reforms. This phenomenon is not unique to the regions studied but can also be observed in other areas like Africa, South Asia, or Latin America, which possess distinct socio-political structures. Hence, the notion of ‘exceptionalism’ often attributed to the MENA region, which has been used to argue both its incompatibility with democratic principles and the supposed ineffectiveness of applying standard analytical tools, methods, and theories, is effectively challenged. This critique opens the door to a more nuanced understanding and examination of the region’s electoral processes and political dynamics, underscoring the universal applicability of democratic analysis and reform. ♦

References

Garnett, Holly Ann, Toby S. James, Madison MacGregor, and Sofia Caal-Lam. 2023. *Year in Elections Global Report 2023*. The Electoral Integrity Project.